

THE STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF THE BEHAVIOUR OF WET ARCHAEOLOGICAL WOOD DURING THE DRYING PROCESS: THE DEVELOPMENT OF DRYING METHODS WITHOUT THE NEED OF CONSOLIDANTS OR PLASTICIZERS

Cláudio MONTEIRO

Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro University & Polytechnic Institute of Tomar
claudio.monteiro.cr@gmail.com

Abstract: *This presents the results of an ongoing research project on the preservation of water-saturated archaeological wood. The aim of this project is, firstly, to better understand the morphology and behaviour of wet archaeological wood when it is subjected to dehydration processes. Secondly, it aims to develop specific drying methods to control the damage caused by drying. To make this possible, a prototype of a chamber for environmental conversion has been developed in order to test drying methods used on materials recovered from water-soaked environments without, however, making use of/resorting to using consolidants.*

Keywords: *Conservation – Wood – Drying – Underwater archaeology – Organic matter*

Résumé: *Le but de cet article est de présenter un projet de recherche en cours sur la préservation de l'eau saturée en bois archéologique. Ce projet est destiné à comprendre la morphologie et le comportement des bois archéologiques humides lorsqu'ils sont soumis à des processus de déshydratation ainsi que de développer des méthodes spécifiques de séchage pour contrôler les dommages causés par le séchage. Pour ce faire, un prototype d'une chambre pour la conversion de l'environnement a été développé pour tester des méthodes de séchage utilisées sur les matériaux récupérés à partir des environnements d'eau sans la nécessité d'utiliser des agents de consolidation.*

Mots-clés: *Conservation – Bois – Séchage – Archéologie sous-marine – Organique*

RESEARCH AIMS

This research project focuses on the conservation of wet archaeological wood.

Our aim is to study the behaviour of wet degraded wood during the drying process and to develop methods which will allow for the dehydration of wood without resorting to the addition of consolidants or filling resins. For this purpose we have developed a new method that will allow for the regeneration of wood tissues, unlike what occurs in traditional consolidation processes.

INTRODUCTION

Ever since work on the conservation of underwater archaeological materials began, conservators have attempted to stabilise and to dry wood artefacts and at the same time causing the least amount of damage. The conservation of organic materials, and particularly wood, has proved to be a real scientific challenge, although many problems have already been solved as a result of the advances in conservation science. However, all the methods developed so far have revealed some fundamental drawbacks, either because they are too aggressive to be used on artefacts or because of the consequences they will have or might have in the long term. What is more, many projects are not feasible because of the size of the artefacts or because of the exorbitant cost of treatments.

The aim of this paper is to make better known the preliminary results of an ongoing research project on a new approach to the conservation of archaeological wood.

Wood is a natural polymer with unique properties and for that it should be studied in-depth, examined and very well understood. Its behaviour and its reactions in the face of external stimuli (inner property of wood) suggest that it can be induced to attain a certain altered state when external stimuli are oriented in a different direction. This treatment strategy rests on the presupposition that wood should be treated as a polymer and not with polymers.

THE CONSERVATION OF SATURATED ARCHAEOLOGICAL WOOD

Over the years, significant progress has been made in the technologies behind the conservation of saturated archaeological wood. First there were developed the drying methods with natural solvents and oils, then new advantages led to the rosin method and to the PEG resins (Astrup 1994; Hamilton 1999; Olvera 2001) after appeared the lyophilisation (Hamilton 1999; Schindelholz 2007), more recently was adapted the process of drying with supercritical fluids (Teshirogi 2001; Lumia *et al.*, 2003; Schindelholz 2007) and the use of silicon oils (Hamilton 1999; Smith 2003).

However, although the results from these technologies are satisfactory and acceptable, they are not without their

disadvantages and they also have side effects on the artefacts treated. Logistics and financial constraints are crucial issues as the conservation of these materials involves extremely high, and sometimes the costs are exorbitant. Size is also a constraint that remains to be overcome. Even the case of the Swedish ship *Vasa* is far from being a success case (Baglioni *et al.*, 2006). Preservation *in situ* has been a sensible solution and we believe it is an idea to retain and further develop (Lillie and Smith 2009).

The PEG resins it is the most common method. This process presents one major drawback, that is the fact that the object cannot be brought back to its original size (Olvera 2001), which consequently prevents any reconstruction of composite objects; If we accept the assumption that these are very aggressive chemical treatments, then the fact that they cause significant changes in the artefacts would be another drawback (Baglioni *et al.*, 2006).

Lyophilisation is an attractive method but it does not dispense of the use of PEG (Jesen 2002). Its application to large-size artefacts is difficult because the use of an air-tight chamber capable of producing very negative temperatures and control pressures becomes progressively more difficult as the size of the artefact increases, and this makes this sort of equipment financially prohibitive.

Even though it has revealed some very interesting results (Hamilton 1999; Smith 2003), the use of drying with silicon oils is compromised when it comes to large-size artefacts, this on account of the logistics, the products and the equipment involved in the process.

Although it has also provided some very good results (Teshirogi 2001; Schindelholz 2007), drying with supercritical fluid has the drawbacks of requiring solvents and of being difficult to use in large-scale treatments. The reasons are the same as for the ones described for lyophilisation, although, in this case, these do not have to do with low temperatures, but rather with the difficulty of controlling pressure in large chambers.

TREATMENT IN ENVIRONMENTAL CONVERSION CHAMBER

This method was designed so as to overcome some of the disadvantages of the existing processes. For this purpose, a chamber has been built which has special characteristics that induce certain inputs into environmental control. The aim of this method is to reconditioning existing wood tissues by means of a specific drying program. The expected result is a dried wood with a natural look and resistance.

In order to understand this process, we must first understand wood behaviour. The wood when immersed in alkaline or acidic water, suffers a slow hydrolysis (Klock 2005) in which the final result is the dispersion of

the monomers that forming the cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Although, this turns out to be a very slow process in the archaeological degradations contexts, being overtaken by bacterial deterioration which consumes the polymers.

Of the three wood polymers, lignin is the one that preserves best and it is, in part, because of this that wood artefacts do not disintegrate. However, during the drying process the loss of cellulose and hemicellulose content in the cell walls causes, not only the loss of resistance in the walls, but also an imbalance of stress forces within the wood tissues. This situation becomes critical when drying is rapid because it causes an imbalance in moisture gradients and promotes an anisotropic behaviour in wood. Our main concern has been, therefore, to understand how this can be overcome. We have focused on creating an artificial environment that promotes controlled, balanced drying, and which eliminates all the stresses caused by asymmetrical dehydration and allows wood to maintain appropriate balance gradients. Another significant factor to be taken into account is the drying rate: this will be the lower, whenever tissues are in a more fragile state. Low temperatures in this case are extremely important because the mechanical resistance of wood increases and, consequently, its resistance to collapsing. This means that the lower the temperature, the bigger the drying rate can be.

Drying is thus carried out by taking into account the properties of the wood and its moisture content and level of degradation, each time using a specific dry programme adapted to each individual case. In our chamber have been tested some theoretical drying models to try to figure what really happens in the reality to the woods elements.

The first program tested was a binary one which is carried out over two phases. An initial phase conducted by drying by evaporation and another one made by a thermal conduction applied alternately (figure 1). Theoretically, this process allows a slow and gradual dehydration interspersed with balanced thresholds of moisture gradients. Together with heat treatment, this process allows for the re-polymerisation of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin without changing the shape and dimensions of form, thereby permitting their reconstruction, glueing and assemblage.

This programme permits the reduction of stresses created by the differences in moisture gradients inside the wood, thus preventing it from collapsing or cracking. On the other hand, the low drying rate and the balance thresholds offset the capillary stress exerted by water, thus preventing cells from collapsing during drying. Another advantage of this process is that it permits the correction of deformations caused by track twists (figure 2 and 3). These deformations have been able to be corrected in primary tests.

In the treatment plans carried out so far, some side effects continue to be observed; this can be accounted by the

Figure 1 – Drying program in sample A2

Figure 2 – Wood before treatment¹

Figure 3 – Wood after treatment

difficulty that the prototype has in meeting the requirements of the theoretical model, in particular the rigor of the values of humidity and temperature.

Because of a lack of funding for this project, the environmental conversion chamber is very rudimentary, which makes it difficult to use more complex drying programmes, as well as to obtain better more reliable data.

SAMPLES BEING HANDLED

Test treatments have been used on two types of samples:

a. Lab-degraded samples:

Pinus Pinaster samples were degraded in an alkaline solution of sodium hydroxide, heated at 60°C for 48 hours and then left in the solution for 5 months.

¹ Wood degraded in sodium hydroxide at 60°C.

b. Archaeological samples:

The samples are from the Portuguese sites Ria de Aveiro A and Ria de Aveiro F and are courtesy of DANS (Nautical and Underwater Archaeology Division) of IGESPAR (Institute for the Management of Architectural and Archaeological Heritage).

The wood samples tested so far are *Pinus Pinaster* and *Betula Alba* (although identification of the latter is still in doubt because of its advanced state of decay).

This paper will focus primarily on the treatment carried out on a *Betula Alba* sample with an estimated moisture content of about 667.7%. It is a Class 1 in terms of decay. Its deterioration is generalized; it looks spongy and has been subjected to the attacks of soft-rot fungi.

Its condition is extremely fragile and when it is dried in the air, such as it was done in the initial test, it reaches a critical rate of deformation and becomes simply unrecognisable.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Despite the fact that these were test conditions and even though this was our first test, we suggest that these are very promising results, even if they are not completely satisfactory in relation to the expected outcomes.

The information data stemming from these works is of considerable interest to the scientific community:

- First, wood has the capacity to reconditioning itself by recovering its mechanical resistance. This is the result of dehydration: when wood dries, the natural polymers in the wood tissues crystallise and recover its physical properties. In fact, the hardness observed in the sample after it has been dried was quite impressive. While in

Figure 4 – A1 Before

Figure 5 – A1 After

Figure 6 – A2 Before

Figure 7 – A2 After

the case of the air-dried sample (which we shall refer to as A1 – figure 4 and 5) the hardness could have been caused by compression resulting from cells collapsing, in the case of the chamber-dried sample (which we shall refer to as A2 – figure 6 and 7) this could not have applied as the pores of medium-size vessels and cells remained unchanged.

- Another relevant detail has to do with the fragmentation of the wood after drying up. Differently from sample A2, despite its hardness sample A1-broke up easily in the axial direction. This could be on account of the extreme fragility of the cell walls given that in sample A1 these are very fragmented as a result of their collapse. Fragmentation seems to occur at the folding points in the cell walls and the deformation stress causes the disruption of fibres in the cell wall tissues (figure 8). In sample A2, the fact that wall tissue seems to have remained intact could be explain of the increased cohesion of the cells (figure 9).
- Regarding sample deformation, there was a significant increase in air drying, A1 took 6 days to dry in a winter environment at temperatures between 12 and 17 degrees Celsius and a R.H. of about 50% and 70%. The end result was a piece of wood which was unrecognisable on account of its high deformation. The A2 sample showed only a slight deformation when compared to A1. The overall shape of the sample was maintained; however, it did not attain the level of exact shape that was desired. It is worth noting that, when analysed under a microscope, the vessels and cells in the wood tissue appear to be intact and to have been preserved. So far we have not yet been able to examine the samples under the electronic microscope, and

Figure 8 – A1 After being dried 40x

Figure 9 – A2 After being dried 40x

therefore cannot yet draw any conclusions about the behaviour of small-diameter cells.

- The deformation of sample A2 suggests that part of the fibres and fibro-tracheids collapsed and that this was the cause of the deformation. Considering that the diameters of these cells are significantly smaller than the vessels and tracheids, the forces resulting from capillary tension are also significantly greater. Theoretically, this problem could be solved through a more rigorous programme involving the reduction of temperature range and humidity.
- When we turn to contraction rate, we see that the sample A1 is about 70% of its initial volume; because of the deformation it is not possible to determine shrinkage in each of the sections. Sample A2 shows a radial shrinkage of about 22% and a tangential shrinkage of about 33%. In the axial direction no change was observed. These values are above the range of those considered acceptable, but these values may be improved if the collapse of smaller cells which leads to an increase in volume is prevented.
- The relationship between the fibre saturation point (FSP) and wood shrinkage is of little consequence when applied to water-saturated, degraded wood. In cases like these there is no matching pattern and neither is it possible to establish a fixed threshold. This relationship is also very difficult to establish in very degraded woods because of the severe deformation caused by collapsing. *Pinus Pinaster* samples which were degraded in the laboratory with a moisture content of 240% revealed an FSP of about 80%, which contrasts with the 30% normally seen in fresh young wood. These values should, in part, come as no surprise, given that FSP in green wood's is not the saturation point of fibres, but is, instead, partial, in the sense that fibres might not be at their maximum saturation capacity, unlike what happens with wood from underwater settings. These studies need to be further refined.
- Another point to bear in mind when comparing sample A1 and A2 is that A2 shows some internal cracks

Figure 10 – B1 Before starting process

Figure 13 – B2 Before starting process

Figure 11 – B1 During process

Figure 14 – B2 During process

Figure 12 – B1 Final Phase of process

Figure 15 – B2 Final Phase of process

(figures 13, 14 and 15) which suggests that the moisture gradients were not properly balanced and caused inner stresses. On the other hand, internal cracking was observed in A1 (figures 10, 11 and 12). This type of anomaly is on account of the fact that the drying technique used in A2 eliminates drying through capillary flow, i.e. the cross-section is insulated so as not to allow water flow in the axial direction, forcing the water to flow through pores and cell walls. Understanding this behaviour is crucial if anisotropy in wood is to be reduced during the drying process because the relationship between tangential and radial drying is much more balanced than the relationship that these two have with axial drying. The capillary flow is tens or even hundreds of times faster, because the obstacles that need to be overcome by the water are substantially smaller in the longitudinal direction. For that reason it appears that the control of moisture gradients is easier with this method.

In order to understand this drying dynamic, two samples were tested in a drying oven at 60°C, one under free drying conditions (B1) and the other with insulated tops (B2). B1 did not suffer greater shrinkage than B2, but no internal cracking was observed.

Although also deformed, B2 had a smaller contraction rate which contributed to a smaller deformation. However, there was the formation of a huge crack which started in the external surface and spread inside, finally closing in the peripheral area. This occurred because regular drying takes place from outside to inside. When the outer area dries, the inner area is still damp and swollen. Because it loses water much faster, the shrinking process starts more quickly in the external area. Differences in volume between these two areas cause cell disruption and the resultant internal and external cracking (Hoadley 1999).

In contrast to this, the drying in B1 was much faster and homogeneous because of the small axial length of the sample. However, the high drying rate caused the significant collapse of cells.

This trial experiment intended to demonstrate the water diffusion dynamics in wood during the drying process. In a real situation, i.e. with a bigger specimen, the two drying types (B1 and B2) actually / would actually / may

coexist, causing asymmetrical drying. For that reason, top insulation becomes all the more important, the greater the fragility of wood.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained so far revealed themselves to be promising and have opened the avenues for advances in further research. If this method proves to be viable, it will become invaluable in the preservation of artefacts from our underwater heritage in that it will reduce costs and the associated logistical problems while, at the same time, contributing to a more ecological and stable treatment of archaeological objects. In addition, treatment time could be significantly reduced given that has been predicted that 3 cm-thick wood specimens samples, no matter what their length is, can be treated in less than 6 months.

The size of objects should not be an obstacle, and the greatest expenditure will be in the construction of the environmental conversion chamber, although the greater its use, the more profitable it will be. The advantage of this chamber is that it can be built in large sizes, thus allowing for the treatment of several objects at any one time.

The fact that one of our objectives is not to use consolidants does not mean that a consolidant cannot be used in extreme situations. However, concentrations of these consolidants may be much smaller than those used to date.

We believe that this method, if further improved, will be very effective in wood with a moisture content of up to 400%.

References

- ASTRUP, E.E. (1994) – A Medieval Log House in Oslo – Conservation of Waterlogged Softwoods with Polyethylene Glycol. *Proceedings of the 5th ICOM Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Portland, Maine. 16-2- August 1993.* p. 41-50.
- BAGLIONI, Michele; POGGI, Giovanna (2006) – Degradation and Conservation of the Wood of the Vessel: The New Frontiers of Chemistry for the Conservation of the Shipwreck of the Swedish Fleet of the XVII Century, *Rivista On line Associazione Italiana Esperti in Diagnostica Applicata ai Beni Culturali* Numero 1 I Semestre.
- HAMILTON, Donny L. (1999) – *Methods of conserving Archaeological Material from Underwater Sites*, Nautical Archaeological Program, Department of Anthropology, Texas A&M University Press, College Station.
- HOADLEY, Bruce R. (1997) – *Understanding Wood, A Craftsman's guide to wood technology*, Taunton Press, Inc. U.S.A.
- JESSEN, Poul; JORGENSEN, Grethe; SCHNELL, Ulrich (2002) – Dynamic LV-SEM Analyses of Freeze Drying Processes for Waterlogged Wood, *Proceedings of the 8th ICOM Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Stockholm, 11-15 June 2001.* p. 319-333.
- KLOCK, Umberto; MUNIZ, Graciela; HERNANDEZ, José; ANDRADE, Alan (2005) – *Química da madeira, 3ª edição*, Universidade Federal do Paraná, Setor de Ciências Agrárias, Departamento de Engenharia e Tecnologia Florestal, Brasil.
- LILLIE, Malcolm; SMITH, Robert (2009) – *International Literature Review: In Situ Preservation of Organic Archaeological Remains*, English Heritage, Wetland Archaeology & Environments Research Centre.
- LUMIA, G.; PERRE, Ch.; SCHRIVE, L.; BARTH, F.; CHAUMAT, G.; ARACIL, J.M. (2003) – Supercritical CO₂ is a Tool For Natural Material Treatments, 6th International Symposium on Supercritical Fluids, ISASF, 28 to 30 April, Versailles, France.
- OLVERA, Alejandra Alonso; REYES, Ma. Teresa Tzompantzi; ANAYA, Demetrio Mendoza (2001) – *Conservación de Maderas Arqueológicas Húmedas: Perspectiva actual y retos para el Futuro en México*, *Conserva* Nº 5. p. 57-79.
- SHINDELHOLZ, Eric (2007) – *An Evaluation of Supercritical and PEG/Freeze Drying of Waterlogged Archaeological Wood*, National Center for Preservation Technology and Training Grant.
- SMITH, C. Wayne (2003) – *Archaeological Conservation Using Polymers, Practical Applications for Organic Artifact Stabilization*, Texas A&M University Press, College Station.
- TESHIROGI, Miho; TAHATA, Eiichiro; KIKUCHI, Mikio; HNOMATA, Hiroshi; KOHDZUMA, Yohsei; KOEZUKA, Takayasu; SAWADA, Masaaki (2001) – Conservation Treatment of Water-logged Wood Whid Supercritical Carbon Dioxide, *Proceedings of the 8th ICOM Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Stockholm, 11-15 June 2001* p. 371-376.